

Integrated Nutrient Supply to Soil for Soil Productivity

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An idea of the nutrients removed from soil by one tonne of grain of paddy and wheat and straw can be obtained from Table 1 (Bhumbla¹).

TABLE 1—NUTRIENTS (kg) REMOVED FROM SOIL BY ONE TONNE OF GRAIN OF PADDY AND WHEAT

Crop	N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O
Paddy	30	12	50
Wheat	35	15	40

The main source of nitrogen in the soil is organic matter. When the soil organic matter content is high, the decomposition of the organic matter may adequately meet the nitrogen needs of the plant. However, under the climatic conditions prevailing in tropical and sub-tropical regions the amount of organic matter in the soil is quite low.

Recycling of plant nutrients would involve use of bulky organic matter and biological nitrogen fixation, along with chemical fertilizers. Currently, this has become very important because of the high fertilizer cost.

Biological nitrogen fixation: One important source of soil nitrogen is nitrogen fixation in the soil, both *symbiotic* and *non-symbiotic*.

Symbiotic nitrogen fixation: The amount of nitrogen fixed by the grain legumes is about 60-80 kg per hectare, most of which is removed in the form of grains. But in fodder legumes like berseem, the fixation may be as high as 400 kg per hectare. The fodder legumes will not only improve the nutrition of the cattle but also result in increased availability of nitrogen in the dung voided by the animals¹.

Non-symbiotic nitrogen fixation: Recent work on non-symbiotic nitrogen fixation in soils growing paddy indicates that the non-symbiotic nitrogen fixation (including blue green algae) may be of the order of 50-60 kg per hectare. Data from permanent manurial experiment in India in the irrigated areas indicate that it is possible to get 1.7 to 2.0 quintals of paddy per hectare without addition of fertilizers, but for any further increase, it would be necessary to supply nutrients in the form of chemical fertilizer or manure or symbiotic nitrogen fixation¹.

Use of chemical fertilizers: The loss of nitrogen from applied nitrogenous fertilizers through leaching and through volatilisation of nitrogen will be considerable and normally the recovery of applied

nitrogen is of the order of 35-60%. Losses of phosphate by leaching or by volatilisation is negligible but the recovery in a crop season may be 20-40%. Continuous addition of phosphatic fertilizers does result in the build up of soil phosphorus which later becomes available to the subsequent crops. Availability of potassium under tropical and sub-tropical conditions of India has been found to depend upon the weatherability of the clay minerals and the potassium needs of the crop.

Because of high prices and shortage of chemical fertilizers the aim should be to obtain maximum return from unit fertilizers applied, rather than maximum yield per unit area. The fertilizer should be applied on the basis of (i) soil test, (ii) crop variety and (iii) expected yield. Placement of fertilizer, split doses and foliar spray under specific soil climatic conditions, may increase the efficiency of fertilizers. The use of nitrogenous fertilizers may be cut down to about 50% of normal requirements, if supplemented by bulky organic manure, particularly in irrigated farming.

Role of organic matter in the soil: Investigations during the last few years in India have shown that periodic addition of large quantities of crop residues to the soil by increased production of plant material through adequate fertilization with inorganic fertilizers will permit nitrogen and organic matter to be maintained at a high level. Jenny and Raychaudhuri² concluded that fertilization with artificial nitrogen compounds is expected to enhance the yields greatly and stimulate the root system in the soil, and these will augment the soil humus and bring it to a new higher steady-state level to benefit plant growth and soil management. Efficient use of chemical fertilizers along with available bulky organic manures and crop residues and sound soil management practices will maintain the level of soil organic matter. From the point of view of soil fertility, it is important to know how much of the organic matter and nitrogen are available for supplying food to the micro-organisms. The supply is considered fair when the ratio is around 20 : 1. When it is reduced to 10 : 1 organic matter is well advanced to a stage where further decomposition will be slow and release and maintenance of nitrogen at high levels is also not possible.

Bulky organic manures also contain growth stimulating and growth regulating substances. However, some materials used in the preparation of the farmyard manure, rural compost or town waste composts, contain toxic substances such as the

heavy metals zinc, copper and nickel which if present in excess in the bulky organic manure can adversely affect plant growth.

The common forms of bulky manures are :

A. Recycling animal, human, vegetation and industrial wastes.

- (a) Farmyard manure,
- (b) Digested cowdung,
- (c) Urban compost/Municipal compost :
 - (i) Activated sludge,
 - (ii) Sewage,
- (d) Composts from urban wastes, and
- (e) Composts from slaughter house wastes.

B. Greenmanure.

A. Recycling animal, human, vegetation and industrial wastes :

The main source of bulky organic manure is the dung from the farm animals and the composts prepared from the urban and rural wastes. In addition, the droppings of poultry birds may account for a few million tonnes. The total potential farmyard manure in India has been estimated as 10.8 million tonnes. Assuming that the availability of N, P₂O₅ and K₂O in dung/agricultural wastes is 30, 60 and 70% of that of inorganic fertilizers and the availability of nitrogen in urine is about 50% of the potential amount, the total and available N, P₂O₅ and K₂O in cattle dung, urine and farm wastes in India are given in the Table 2¹.

TABLE 2—POTENTIAL AMOUNT OF TOTAL AND AVAILABLE N, P₂O₅ AND K₂O IN CATTLE DUNG, URINE AND FARM WASTES (MILLION TONNES)

	N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O
Total	2.20	0.82	1.78
Available	0.78	0.49	1.32

(a) *Farmyard manure* : Farmyard manure is a very valuable material for maintaining soil fertility in its widest sense. The upward trend in fertilizer prices has necessitated improvements in the storage and application of farmyard manure so as to make better use of its plant nutrient content. The common farmyard manure is produced from cattle dung, 27 kg per adult animal per day, urine, 18 kg per adult animal per day, and bedding straw estimated at 1.5 kg per adult animal per day.

The overall mean value for the composition of farmyard manure in terms of organic matter and primary and secondary plant nutrients is given in Table 3.

The pH of farmyard manure is usually high (8.0 or higher) due to the presence of ammonia, but when incorporated in the soil it does not greatly

TABLE 3—COMPOSITION OF FARMYARD MANURE AS PERCENTAGE OF FRESH MATERIAL*

Dry matter	Ash free dry matter	Total N	Total P ₂ O ₅	Total K ₂ O	Total MgO	Total CaO
23	17	0.6	0.3	0.7	0.04	0.20

* Source : Organic Manure, Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food, London, Bulletin 210, 1976.

affect the soil pH. Where earliness is important particularly in vegetable crops, application of heavy dressings of farmyard manure along with chemical fertilizers usually gives better results than by using chemical fertilizers alone.

Treatment with farmyard manure increases the biological activity of the soil as is evidenced from the increased rate of evolution of carbon dioxide; earthworm activity in soil is greatly increased, the nodulation of legumes is improved and the population of pathogens causing plant diseases is reduced.

Farmyard manure contains other nutrients including micronutrients, the average level of which is shown in Table 4.

TABLE 4—COMPOSITION OF FARMYARD MANURE (FRESH MATERIAL BASIS)

Nutrient	Content (mg/kg)
Sodium	1000
Chlorine	2000
Iron	180
Manganese	45
Zinc	20
Copper	4
Boron	4
Cobalt	0.3
Molybdenum	0.3
Iodine	0.05

Source : Organic Manure, Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food, London, Bulletin 210, 1976.

Dean^a analysed the yield records of Pusa Permanent Manurial-cum-Rotation Experiments for selected treatments with farmyard manure, NPK, and NP which are summarised in Table 5.

TABLE 5—AVERAGE YIELD (kg/acre) IN PUSA PERMANENT MANURIAL-CUM-ROTATION EXPERIMENTS, 1930-57

Crop	Treatment			No Manure
	FYM*	NPK	NP	
Total Annual	1920	1462	1253	449
Maize	1020	656	419	213
Pigeon pea	1086	940	1076	386
Peas	584	463	477	145
Wheat	905	724	651	241
Barley	1001	1066	1090	343

*FYM was applied to supply 44.8 kg N/ha.

The yields of FYM plot have been maintained at higher level of annual production than rest of the treatments. The yields of barley and pigeon pea have been materially influenced by phosphate

applied to the soil, of peas and wheat to a slightly lesser extent. Potash appears to be limiting for the yield of maize.

(b) *Digested cowdung*: Cowdung cakes are widely used as fuel in Indian villages. The proportion of dung used for preparing cowdung cakes varies in different States in India from 30-50%. Heat efficiency of dung cakes is low and burning of cowdung cakes give rise to smoke. Further, as the cakes are used as fuel only, the plant nutrients in the dung are wasted.

Cowdung gas or biogas is the gas derived from cowdung and other natural farmyard waste by anaerobic fermentation. A biogas plant consists of a digester and a gas holder. The fuel gas from the biogas plant has the following composition:

TABLE 6
Composition of Biogas (%)

Methane	50-60
Hydrogen	5-10
Carbon dioxide	30-45
Nitrogen	1-2

The fuel gas can be used for heating or lighting or as motive power. The range of N, P₂O₅ and K₂O content of the residual slurry on dry basis is as follows:

TABLE 7
Composition of Biogas Slurry (%)

N	1.4 to 1.8
P ₂ O ₅	1.1 to 2.0
K ₂ O	0.8 to 1.2

In addition, digested slurry contains a fair amount of essential micronutrients. The slurry is rich in humus and easily mixes with the soil. It prevents breeding of flies and is free from odour which is usually associated with compost manure (Biswas⁴).

It is not economic to set up even the smallest size biogas plant (2 cubic metres) unless 40 kg fresh dung is available daily. The cowdung should be mixed with equal quantity of water before it is fed into the gas plant which should be located near the kitchen in an open area exposed to the sun for a greater part of the day. The ground water level at the site should be at least 4 metres below the surface throughout the year. Besides producing fuel gas and manure, the biogas plant provides local sanitation.

Comparative advantages of cowdung composted in manure pit, cakes for fuel and dung digested in a biogas plant in one year from 45 kg of fresh cattle dung per day can be seen from Table 8 (Rao⁵).

(c) *Urban compost/municipal compost*: The urban/municipal compost from sewage purification system consists of two broad types: (i) activated sludge and (ii) sewage.

TABLE 8—COMPARATIVE ANNUAL ADVANTAGES OF UTILISATION OF 45 kg OF FRESH CATTLE DUNG PER DAY

Method of utilisation	Amount of fuel obtained	Effective heat value	Amount of manure
Composted in manure pit	Nil	Nil	7 cartloads
Converted into cakes for fuel	3.65 tonnes	1.55 million k cal	—
Digested in biogas plant	620 m ³	1.87 million k cal	10 cartloads

1 cartload = 2 tonnes (approx.)

(i) *Activated sludge*: In India, as in other parts of the world, the growth of cities is on the increase and the problem of efficient utilisation of sludge and sewage is assuming increasing importance. In large cities where area for cultivation is limited some of the sewage is wasted or improperly utilised. In recent years activated sludge plants have been installed to make the best use of town wastes. The composition of activated sludge is given in Table 9 (Das⁶).

TABLE 9—COMPOSITION OF ACTIVATED SLUDGE (ON DRY BASIS)

Item	%
Loss on ignition	76.77
Mineral matter	53.23
Sand and Silica	36.74
Nitrogen	4.12
P ₂ O ₅	2.24
K ₂ O	0.95
CaO	2.87
MgO	2.20
Fe ₂ O ₃	4.96

The sludge contains approximately 50% organic matter and has C : N ratio 11.7 : 1. Of its nitrogen, 26 to 34% undergoes mineralization in 4-6 weeks as compared to 30-44% in oilcake in 6-8 weeks time. Thus its rate of mineralisation is quite high. Municipal sludge often contains undesirable chemicals which may be toxic to plant and/or eventually toxic to animals and human beings that consume edible parts of such plants.

(ii) *Sewage*: Manurial value of Poona sewage was investigated by Talati⁷ and the results are given in Table 10. When directly applied to the

TABLE 10—COMPOSITION OF POONA SEWAGE (PARTS PER 100,000)

Season	Free and saline ammonia	Albuminoid ammonia	Total N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	CaO	Dispersed solid
Hot weather	2.51	0.92	3.43	1.350	0.521	14.287	44.10
Monsoon	2.36	0.79	3.15	1.737	0.377	13.844	44.10
Winter	2.41	0.84	3.25	1.969	0.396	14.008	53.30

field without sedimentation it contains about 44-53 parts per 100,000 solids, of which about 50% is organic suspension. Sewage farming is more

profitable when quick growing crops of leafy nature are grown. Sewage containing industrial effluent may contain zinc, copper, nickel and possibly cadmium above their toxic limits.

(d) *Compost from urban wastes*: Urban compost preparation consists in the collection of all town wastes like sweepings, garbage, household rubbish, night soil, etc. and allowing them to decompose in trenches by the Bangalore method. All these wastes when composted in trenches yield a good bulky organic manure of high quality, quite rich in fertilizing elements including micronutrients such as copper, zinc, manganese and boron. The manure so obtained is quite innocuous and safe to handle and apply to the soil. Urban compost gives very high yields of crops grown under irrigation viz., vegetables, potatoes sugarcane, rice, banana, etc. Urban compost has been used effectively for the reclamation of saline and alkali soils also.

(e) *Manure from slaughter house wastes*: Bones, bloodmeal hoof and horn-meal and meat-meal constitute the main slaughter house wastes. These provide useful sources of manure wherever available. In India the bloodmeal, hoof and horn-meal, which are at present used for manurial purposes can amount to about 0.25, 0.06 and 0.06 million tonnes per annum providing 0.025, 0.0066 and 0.0048 million tonnes of nitrogen, respectively.

B. Greenmanure :

Greenmanuring in irrigated tracts with adequate size of holding has been found to be beneficial in India for paddy and sugarcane. The approximate amount of nitrogen turned under by some of the greenmanure crops is given in Table 11 (Mirchandani and Khan⁶).

TABLE 11—AMOUNT OF NITROGEN TURNED UNDER BY SOME GREENMANURE CROPS

Greenmanure crop	kg N/ha turned under
<i>Crotalaria juncea</i> (Sannhemp)	84.0
<i>Sesbania aculeata</i> (Dhaincha)	77.2
<i>Cyamopsis tetragonoloba</i> (Guar)	62.4
<i>Vigna sinensis</i> (Cowpea)	56.3
<i>Phaseolus aureus</i> (Moong)	38.6

Greenmanuring has, in most parts of the world, been applied more successfully to increase the available nitrogen supply than the humus content of the soil. Thus Singh⁹ has shown on the basis

TABLE 12—ORGANIC CARBON CONTENT OF SOIL (%)

Treatment	1940-41	1947-48	1954-55	1957-58
Control	0.223	0.212	0.229	0.280
NPK	0.235	0.292	0.245	0.365
Green-manure	0.228	0.291	0.257	0.358
Green-manure + P	0.300	0.315	0.261	0.430

of the data of the Pusa Permanent Manurial trial started in 1908, that greenmanuring has not resulted in any great change in the organic carbon content of the Pusa soil (Table 12).

These data show that the content of organic carbon in the control plots has remained practically constant. Purely greenmanure plots have maintained a slightly higher organic carbon content, but the plots receiving inorganic fertilizers have maintained a higher level of organic carbon. The greenmanure plots receiving phosphorus, maintained the highest content of organic carbon.

Yardstick of response to bulky organic manure: A large number of results obtained from a number of Government farms and experimental stations show that the farmyard manure, when properly prepared, can give increased yield ranging from 10-50%. The results of All India Coordinated Agronomic Experiments Scheme averaging over 3-4 years indicate that generally, application of farmyard manure at the rate of 75 tonnes per hectare gave increase of annual grain yield of rice and wheat in fixed rotation, ranging from 5 to 9 quintals per hectare. Much better results can be obtained when application of farmyard manure is made in combination with other practices of good management such as improved seed, proper crop rotation and supplementary fertilizers. For obtaining economic return, the use of chemical nitrogenous fertilizers may be cut down by 50% by using in combination with bulky organic manure.

Environmental pollution: The promotion of integrated plant nutrients as outlined above would help in solving the severe problems of environmental pollution of soil, water and atmosphere which are bound to be faced as the pace of development and exploitation of resources is increased. Indeed, for tackling the problem of environmental pollution, there is no alternative to efficient and economic basic resource conservation measures on a national scale.

Recent trend: In more recent years Government of India have stressed on the usefulness of integrated nutrient supply to soils for maintaining and building up sustained soil productivity. The experiments of Professor N. R. Dhar and his coworkers at the Sheila Dhar Institute of Soil Science, University of Allahabad, have established that application of organic matter along with rock phosphate fixes atmospheric nitrogen in the soil and leads to increase in its nitrogen status. This is a cheap and convenient method of improving soil fertility and needs trials on pilot project scale in different soil climatic regions. Fundamental work on different types of bulky organic matter including green-manure, rural compost, town compost, sewage, sullage and industrial wastes like press-mud etc. is urgently called for.

Conclusion: The high prices of chemical fertilizers and the shortage of energy have made it urgent to show the farmers the way to increase

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productivity by using less fertilizers. A significant development in this direction is the recycling of organic wastes. Indeed, there has been over-emphasis in the past on the use of chemical fertilizers to boost agricultural production. Use of chemical fertilizers along with organic manure would maintain the fertility of the soil and increase crop production. Field trials show that about 50% of chemical fertilizers needed on the basis of soil test could be saved in irrigated farming if used judiciously along with bulky organic manures.

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